

EFFECTIVE METHODS OF TEACHING ENGLISH TO CHILDREN OF THE YOUNG AGE TROUGH GAMES

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ABSTRACT

The methods of teaching and language acquisition are changing and becoming more flexible and effective toward young learners. Moreover, teaching trough game-based program is becoming more popular and beneficial ensuring comprehensive style of teaching. This article she the lights on various effective methods several partys of language aspets.

INTRODUCTION

Teaching language trough gamification has gained great popularity for last few decades due to it enhances not only physical ability of the learners but also has impact on phycological and mental development at the same time. According to the teachers' points of view by far the most challenging stage of teaching, definitely from 1st to 4th grade since children of the young age do not have long-term attention span therefore they might easily be distracted by more interesting things such as talking with classmates or using mobile. It is undeniable that simple teaching activities from the books of English such as Guess What are not effective enough to evoke higher enthusiasm of learners whereas relaxing atmosphere and effect can be obtained trough games.

The aim of this article to shed the light on various game-based methods and platforms to aid both teachers and learners to relieve the tension in the process of teaching and acquiring knowledge for young age learners.

Stronin MF (1981) [2] claims that, there are many types of games, but among them the following group can be distinguished:

- Phonetic
- Lexical
- Games with phrases
- Grammar games
- Games for teaching reading
- Games for listening
- Games for teaching speaking
- Mixed games
- Communication games

MTERIALS AND METHODS

Language is regarded as an essential item in language games which various language skills can be developed. Creating games according to the topic means relevant and finding them in online platform is not as challenging as it was before, only with a few clicks of the button it is possible for teachers to be ready for the lesson because of the technological advancements offer a number of possible solutions. Online websites allow teachers to modify the games to fit learners' needs, according to the game groups above for example, among phonetic games we can use texts for imitation, completion task or Q&A activities.

Lexical plays a significant role in the process of learning a language therefore in the starting point, if there is a strong building block of lexis, learners are less likely to face more difficulties. Games for vocabulary expansion can be played on a daily basis in each lesson as a revision of learned new vocabulary. For instance, if the topic was about animals, they can play "Hot Seat" through this game children unconsciously revise the type of the animal and create questions relating to them. The rules of the game are simple, teacher should choose one volunteer to be first, and show one type of animal to the class which the first volunteer is supposed to find it by asking questions such as "Is it a fast animal?" "Where is their habitat?" "What do they usually eat?" in this way continue with rest of the members of the class too.

Games with phrases are mostly suitable for learners having more background information about the language and online games such as "Wordwall", "Jeopardy" or Matching activities can be created for practicing phrases of English languages. As an example, for matching activity can be the word "**take care**" – care for someone, learners should match phrases with the appropriate definition which helps them not only memorize one word, but also understand the explanation in English not in word for word translation.

Undoubtedly, grammar activities make pupils feel fear, because of various structure with exceptions, however it should be considered as the crucial aspect of the language and attempt to revise them a few lessons. Particularly, tenses of English language make learners feel confused and in some cases the majority neglect this part. If the simple words from books are superseded into the online platform with multiple choices or selecting words from the box, it is highly likely to grab more attention, as young learners quickly react to colorful things.

Teaching reading to children is neither effective nor easy to explain, if the text contains only words learners can feel demotivated, therefore first of all the proper text should be given or games that simulate real life situations, for example, "At an appointment with an eye doctor", "TV announcer competition" or "Playing the computer" Bacharova LN (1996) [2]

Speaking activities in English language for some children seem to be as a horror movie. According to Rao (2019) [1], English teachers need to use different techniques to develop their speaking skills because some EFL/ESL learners are deeply afraid of making mistakes. As a result of the fear or feeling being laughed by their peers, when teacher simply wants to ask for questions about the topic at the beginning of the lesson, more than half of the group say no word and tend to listen only ideas of others. Therefore, in order to make them feel motivated the proper approach can be in game based format, which evokes the interest for speaking and they unconsciously get involved in the game. For instance, "Picture description", "Who Am I?" or "Snowball" are very common games.

CONCLUSION

Games are considered as a prominent part of the lesson particularly at the beginning and at the end of the lesson, to warm up learners in order to engage them in the lesson, or as a revision of the new topic at the end. In accordance with varying topics of lesson plan, divergent games can be modified through competence and creativity on the teacher. Motivating them mentally,

physically, expanding their knowledge, developing memory all of this demand proper approach in which games have great contribution secondly after mentor.

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